

Preliminary summary on data needs

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1. What methods are you developing (or applying) for risk analysis/risk assessment?

POLYRISK: Integrated Approaches to Testing and Assessment (IATA)	PlasticHeal: policy-relevant risk assessment framework for MNP	IMPTOX: biomonitoring	PlasticsFatE: Prospective multi criteria decision support system (PMCDs)	PlasticsFatE: Integrated Approaches to Testing and Assessment (IATA)	PAPILLONS: ecological risk assessment in soil
logical combinations of tests and assessments	what kind of nanorisk assessment frameworks can be used for human health risk assessment of MNPs	biological samples, cell studies, animal studies, clinical study (spectroscopy)	early/prospective risk assessment	testing and assessment	usage of standard OECD derived tests, field experiments

2. What type of data are needed?

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IATA and decision nodes asks for input	data about populations, DNELs, MoA, reproductive toxicity	dietary and lifestyle habits, clinical data (personal and family history, allergy study)	polymer type and field of application	knowledge on fundamental mechanisms	physical-chemical characterization of MNPs

3. What sources do you use to obtain the data?

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mainly experimental	guidelines on precautionary matrix for synthetic nanomaterials, Environmental Defense & DuPont NanoRisk Framework	field work: clinical study recruitment, clinical facilities, animal facilities	scientific literature, databases	data generated within the PlasticsFatE project	agricultural census, industry databases, farmer and stakeholder interviews

4. Are there any problems in collecting these data?

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lack of a systematic collection of particles of MNP to test them	Information for all MNPs and their respective additives	establishing mice models, collecting biological samples, follow up in the clinical study	opposing results within independent publications	data formats (missing calculated effect concentrations)	little existing/available data

Six tools with different scope of risk analysis

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real world scenarios (tire rubber)	ensuring policy relevance	acute toxicological and other more subtle effects of MNPs on human health	designed to use early indicators and deals with data gaps & uncertainties	hypothesis-driven based on knowledge of fundamental mechanisms	in vitro experiments, standard OECD derived tests

Thank you for your attention

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